

PROBLEMS OF LEARNING BILINGUALISM

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Abstract. This article presents information about the emergence of bilingualism, scientists who have studied the phenomenon of bilingualism to this day, and their works. At the same time, its connection with other disciplines and scientific research.

Keywords: Bilingualism, bilingualism, linguistic communication, linguistic consciousness, sociolinguist, sociolinguistics, psycholinguist, Psycholinguistics, extralinguistic, neurolinguistics, linguoculturology.

INTRODUCTION

The issues of linguistic communication occupy an important place in the context of the rapidly growing science and technology in our country, the Internet networks that have entered our lives, and at the same time, Uzbekistan has extensive cultural and political relations with many countries of the world. Today, based on the wide opportunities created in the field of education, the number of students studying or continuing their studies in foreign countries is growing rapidly. This, in turn, causes the demand and interest in foreign languages to increase. Bilingualism as a phenomenon has its roots in the ancient world, where languages interacted through migration, trade, and conquest. The phenomenon of bilingualism has been actively studied since the 19th century. We can find the first information about this in Humboldt's "Selected Works on Linguistics" and "The Nature of Language and the

Nature of the People”, Piaget's “Psycholinguistics in Essays and Extracts” [3.2003.232-248]. The study of this phenomenon, which was initially carried out within the framework of comparative historical linguistics, was gradually integrated into various psychological and linguistic theories by Saussure, Boudin de Courtenay, Bogoroditsky, and later Potebnya in his work “Esthetics and Poetics”[4.1976.614]. Bilingualism means that a person is bilingual or communicates effectively between two languages. This can take many forms, such as actively using two languages while learning multiple languages, learning multiple languages naturally during childhood, or acquiring them artificially after acquiring the mother tongue. Bilingualism can foster cultural understanding, expand career opportunities, and also greatly contribute to the development of intellectual diversity. If we understand bilingualism as the process of mastering the linguistic and cultural code of a foreign language, then any person learning a foreign language can be called an artificial bilingual. If bilingualism is considered as a result of this process, then this phenomenon can be called the ability to use language. A person who knows a foreign language at the same time as his mother tongue is called bilingual person. Scholars usually know the language of their country as well as the language of another the nation and have the opportunity to express their opinions or apply information in practice.

METHODS

In general, the methodological foundations of the study of bilingualism in the 20th century managed to form a large-scale analytical base for the problems of bilingualism, which made it possible to start using it for practical learning and didactic purposes. For example: Vereshchagin's “Language and Culture” and “Psychological and Methodological Studies of Bilingualism”, Vishnevskaya's “Bilingualism and its Aspects”, Karlinsky's “Basics of the Theory of Language Interaction”, Rosenzweig's “Language Relations”, “Problems of Linguistics” and others. “Issues of bilingualism and multilingualism are mainly considered by linguistics” because bilingualism is based on language communication [1.2009. 34],

however, also includes an interdisciplinary approach to bilingualism as a multidimensional phenomenon. The phenomena of bilingualism and the linguistic consciousness of bilinguals are studied by psycholinguistics, sociolinguistics, neurolinguistics and linguocultural sciences. In addition, the linguistic aspect of bilingualism is psychological, pedagogical with psychological, the literary-artistic aspect is closely related to linguistics [6.1988.70]. Sociology studies bilingualism in relation to behavioral problems of bilingual individuals in society.

Psychologists, psycholinguists, and sociologists also study aspects of multilingualism: for example, in psycholinguistics, bilingualism is considered in terms of the relationship between the mechanisms of speech and text, with a strong emphasis on human learning and acquisition. Information about this can be found in the works of Bagana and Vigel. In addition, the problems of bilingualism are often studied from a psychological point of view. Examples of these are the following we can show. Nikulicheva, Karabulatova, Polivara, Rivlina, Chirsheva,

Abutalebi, Green, Baker, Bialystok, Meltson, Carlson, Rodríguez-Fornells provided information on the psychological conditions of the formation of bilingualism, the need to justify the choice of foreign language teaching methods in relation to the type of bilingualism. The positive and negative effects of the mother tongue on learning a foreign language are considered. According to Andreeva, there is an assumption that a bilingual person has one single perceptual system and two separate speech production systems in his native and foreign languages [1.2009. 38]

RESULTS

Contrary to this opinion, A.A. Zalevskaya says: Developing the interface theory of word meaning, which reflects the organization of codes and code transitions from word to image, he concludes that a bilingual person simultaneously has two mental lexicons, each of which is related to one language [5.1996.195]. E. Yu. Myagkova's views are quite different from the two above. Bilingualism speaks of the formation of

a certain interlinguistic consciousness. It includes knowledge about the structure and rules of operation of the language, which helps to compose and interpret the text [7.2006.122-130]. According to RT Bell, bilingualism can be considered a unique and independent communicative system [2.1980.318]

Isaev, Smolya, Angermeyev, Hornberger, Knickerbocker, Altarriba worked on the sociolinguistic aspects of bilingualism. Their scientific research work is mainly devoted to the study of the functions and scope of each language used in bilingualism. Sociolinguists are interested in the spread of bilingualism among professional groups, the problems of language use in various aspects of society, the influence of extralinguistic factors on bilingualism, the formation of bilingual channels, national and international interdependence.

DISCUSSION

The science of pedagogy studies the problems of active and passive bilingualism, as well as the problems associated with the process of teaching a foreign language in a bilingual environment. We can cite Moore, Evnitskaya, Ramos-de Robles, Ovando Combs, Pinter as examples. In the literature, many studies have been conducted on the use of bilingualism from an artistic point of view. The works of Heredia, Altarriba, Cieslicka, Titonelar can be an example of this. In this, not only the analysis of literary works written by bilingual writers and the specific features, positive and negative aspects of the perception of such literature by a bilingual reader, but also the speech characteristics of bilingual characters are given great attention.

Two language systems used by a bilingual person may, on the one hand, function independently of each other, and on the other hand, be interdependent. According to the interdependence of speech mechanisms, bilingualism is divided into two types: pure and mixed. Pure bilingualism implies the use of strictly one language code for one field of activity or one person: for example, bilinguals use one language system in the educational process or at work, and another in everyday communication.

In the case of mixed bilingualism, languages can freely interchange; a speaker moves easily from one language system to another, but there is a mix of words and grammatical structures from one language to another. This type of bilingualism exists in countries where multilingual peoples live in the same area, as well as in families of different nationalities of parents. According to some researchers, bilingualism occurs when a speaker switches from one language code to another in a given communication situation - regardless of whether it is a matter of two national languages, literary languages and dialects, or international languages. The term "bilingualism" means the presence of two languages side by side in the mind of a person, where not only the languages themselves, but also the processes of interaction of language cultures take place. At the same time, sometimes a student learning a foreign language acquires the language so well that he cannot be distinguished from a native speaker of this language.

CONCLUSION

The interest of representatives of different fields of science in bilingualism and the studies showing the theoretical and practical importance of this issue can appear for various reasons, the main of which are the processes of globalization, which has accelerated significantly since the last period. In the middle of the 20th century, there are bilingual (Malta, Canada, Cyprus, Sudan, etc.) and multilingual countries (Russia, Belgium, Switzerland, South Africa, etc.) in the modern world, and the majority of the population of these countries knows two or more languages. At the same time, the number of people in the world who know at least one European language is increasing, so it is understandable that more and more attention is paid to the problems of learning foreign languages based on today's demand.

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